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Title : AI-Based Immersive Virtual Environment as a Behavioral Conditioning Tool in Pediatric Oral Rehabilitation: A Case Report

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Abstract

Background: Behavioral management remains a major challenge in pediatric dentistry, particularly in patients with early childhood caries and severe dental anxiety. While virtual reality has been explored as a distraction tool, its integration as part of a structured behavioral conditioning protocol supported by artificial intelligence (AI)-based immersive environments remains limited. **Case Presentation:** A 5-year-old female patient with early childhood caries and negative behavior (Frankl I) presented with multiple carious lesions requiring comprehensive oral rehabilitation, including pulpectomies. The patient exhibited persistent crying, treatment refusal, and a history of negative dental experiences. **Intervention:** A structured non-pharmacological behavioral management protocol was implemented, including gradual desensitization, tell-show-do, positive reinforcement, and modeling techniques. This approach was complemented by an AI-supported immersive virtual environment developed using FrameVR, enabling experiential reconstruction of the dental process and controlled exposure to anxiety-triggering stimuli. **Results:** The patient demonstrated a progressive behavioral improvement, transitioning from Frankl I to cooperative behavior. This allowed the successful completion of multiple pulpectomies and restorative procedures without pharmacological intervention. The immersive environment enhanced emotional regulation, reduced anticipatory anxiety, and improved understanding of clinical procedures. **Conclusion:** The integration of AI-based immersive virtual environments as an adjunct to behavioral conditioning may represent an effective strategy to improve cooperation and reduce anxiety in pediatric dental patients. This approach has the potential to shift behavioral management from passive distraction to active cognitive-emotional conditioning. This approach may represent a clinically applicable strategy to improve cooperation and reduce anxiety in pediatric dental patients

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1. Introduction

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Pediatric dental care extends beyond the technical management of oral diseases, requiring effective strategies to address children's emotional and behavioral responses during treatment. Early childhood caries (ECC) remains a highly prevalent condition influenced by biological, behavioral, psychosocial, and environmental factors, significantly impacting children's quality of life and their relationship with dental care. [1] In this context, dental anxiety and negative behavioral patterns represent major barriers to successful treatment, particularly in young patients with previous adverse dental experiences. Behavior guidance techniques such as tell-show-do, positive reinforcement, voice control, and modeling are widely recognized as first-line non-pharmacological approaches in pediatric dentistry. Additionally, systematic desensitization has proven effective in gradually reducing fear responses by exposing patients to anxiety-provoking stimuli in a controlled and progressive manner.[2] However, these strategies may be limited in patients with severe anxiety or persistent negative behavior, often leading to the need for pharmacological management, including sedation or general anesthesia. In recent years, digital technologies—particularly virtual reality (VR)—have been introduced as adjunct tools to reduce anxiety during dental procedures, primarily functioning as distraction mechanisms.[3] More recently, the emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) and immersive virtual environments has opened new possibilities for enhancing patient engagement, emotional regulation, and experiential learning. These technologies enable the creation of interactive, patient-centered environments that can simulate clinical scenarios, facilitate cognitive processing of dental experiences, and promote a sense of predictability and control. [4] Despite these advances, current evidence remains limited regarding the integration of AI-based immersive environments as part of a structured behavioral conditioning protocol in pediatric dentistry. Most existing studies focus on VR as a passive distraction tool rather than as an active component of cognitive-emotional restructuring and behavioral modification.[5] Therefore, this case report aims to describe the application of a structured behavioral conditioning and modification protocol, supported by an AI-based immersive virtual environment, in the comprehensive oral rehabilitation of a pediatric patient with early childhood caries and severely negative behavior. This approach seeks to demonstrate how immersive technologies can complement traditional behavioral strategies, facilitating emotional adaptation, improving cooperation, and enabling successful treatment without pharmacological intervention. This report contributes to the emerging paradigm shift

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from passive behavioral distraction toward active cognitive-emotional conditioning supported by immersive technologies.

1. Case Report

A 5-year-old female patient presented to the Dental Care Center of Universidad de Las Américas (CAO-UDLA, Quito, Ecuador) with a chief complaint of spontaneous dental pain. The patient had no relevant medical history. Behavioral assessment using the Frankl Behavior Rating Scale revealed a definitely negative behavior (Frankl I), characterized by persistent crying, refusal of treatment, and resistance to interaction with clinical staff. The patient's caregiver reported previous negative dental experiences, contributing to dental fear and anxiety. (Figure 1)

Figure 1. Upper (A) and lower occlusal (B) intraoral photograph.

2.1 Clinical and Radiographic Findings

Clinical examination revealed multiple carious lesions consistent with early childhood caries (ECC), including a deep occluso-distal lesion in tooth 65 associated with vestibular inflammation. Additional findings included caries affecting teeth 53, 55, 62, 63, 64, 74, 75, and 84, as well as a root remnant of tooth 51. Periapical radiographic evaluation confirmed a deep carious lesion in tooth 65 with proximity to the pulp chamber. Three teeth were diagnosed with irreversible pulp involvement and indicated for pulpectomy.

Extraoral examination showed a dolichofacial pattern with a convex profile and no craniofacial abnormalities. Intraoral findings included Class I occlusion, enamel hypoplasia, and poor oral hygiene associated with frequent intake of cariogenic foods.

2.2 Behavioral Management Protocol 101 102

Given the patient's negative behavior and high anxiety levels, a structured non-pharmacological behavioral management protocol was implemented. Initial sessions were dedicated exclusively to adaptation, without operative intervention. The protocol included: 103
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- Gradual exposure to dental stimuli (from non-invasive to invasive) 107
- Tell-show-do technique 108
- Positive reinforcement 109
- Voice control 110
- Indirect modeling 111

Systematic desensitization was progressively applied, allowing the patient to become familiar with the clinical environment, instruments, and procedures in a controlled and predictable manner. 112
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2.3 Integration of Immersive Virtual Environment 116 117

As an adjunct to behavioral conditioning, an AI-supported immersive virtual environment was developed using FrameVR (<https://framevr.io/casopediatria2>). This environment included two main components: 118
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1. Patient-centered narrative simulation: 121 122

A sequential reconstruction of the dental experience from the patient's perspective, facilitating emotional processing and understanding of the clinical context. 123
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2. Clinical procedure visualization: 125

A structured representation of the procedures performed, including explanation of therapeutic steps and expected sensations, adapted to the patient's cognitive level. This immersive approach enabled controlled exposure to anxiety-triggering stimuli, enhanced predictability, and promoted a sense of control, supporting emotional regulation during treatment. (Figure 2) 126
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Figure 2. Familiarization with the dental chair and gradual exposure of dental stimuli.

2.4 Dental Treatment

Emergency management of tooth 65 was performed through pulpectomy under local anesthesia and rubber dam isolation. Necrotic pulp tissue was removed using manual instrumentation (K-files and Hedström files), followed by irrigation with saline solution and sodium hypochlorite. Intracanal medication with camphorated paramonochlorophenol was applied, and temporary sealing was achieved using Coltosol. Subsequently, definitive restoration was performed using zinc oxide–eugenol as a root canal filling materials filling material, followed by coronal rehabilitation with composite resin (Filtek Z350 XT, 3M®) using an adhesive protocol (Scotchbond Universal Etchant and Tetric N-Bond Universal Adhesive). Due to the patient’s behavioral profile, the remaining pulpectomies were distributed across three separate sessions to minimize emotional overload and reinforce adaptive behavior. Each session incorporated behavioral reinforcement strategies, including verbal encouragement, scheduled breaks, and guided breathing techniques. Additional restorative treatments were completed using composite resin, and fluoride varnish was applied as part of a preventive strategy to address enamel hypoplasia and reduce future caries risk.(Figure 3)

Figure 3. Say-show-do technique (C) Contingent positive reinforcement and voice control (D) Use of imitation models - indirect modeling (E)

2.5 Behavioral and Clinical Outcomes

Progressive behavioral improvement was observed throughout treatment (Table 1). The patient evolved from Frankl I behavior to cooperative behavior, allowing the successful completion of multiple pulpectomies and restorative procedures without the need for pharmacological management. The integration of the immersive virtual environment contributed to a reduction in anticipatory anxiety, improved understanding of procedures, and increased acceptance of treatment. Family involvement reinforced positive behavioral adaptation and adherence to oral health recommendations.(Figure 4,5)

Figure 4. Perspective of the patient living the dental care process

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Figure 5. Virtual environment documenting clinical analysis with the subjective experience of the patient.

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Figure 6. Feeling of control on the part of the patient, decreasing alert response.

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Table 1 . Behavioral progression during treatment

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Session	Frankl Behavior	Intervention	Outcomes
1	I	Adaptation	Persisten Crying

2	II	VR + exposure	Reduced anxiety
3	III	Treatment	Cooperative behavior

3. Discussion

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The management of pediatric patients with early childhood caries (ECC) and severely negative behavior represents a persistent clinical challenge in pediatric dentistry. Dental anxiety at an early age has been strongly associated with reduced cooperation, avoidance behaviors, and long-term negative attitudes toward oral health care. In patients classified as Frankl I, conventional approaches often face limitations, frequently leading to the consideration of pharmacological management, including sedation or general anesthesia. In the present case, a structured behavioral conditioning protocol based on gradual desensitization, tell-show-do, positive reinforcement, and modeling was successfully implemented. [6] This approach aligns with current clinical guidelines, which recommend prioritizing non-pharmacological strategies as first-line management. However, unlike traditional protocols, the present case incorporated an AI-based immersive virtual environment as an adjunctive tool, introducing a novel dimension to behavioral management. Previous studies have primarily evaluated virtual reality (VR) as a distraction technique aimed at diverting the patient's attention during dental procedures. While effective in reducing perceived pain and anxiety, this approach is fundamentally passive and does not necessarily promote long-term behavioral adaptation.[7] In contrast, the immersive environment used in this case functioned as an active cognitive-emotional intervention, allowing the patient to process, reinterpret, and anticipate the dental experience in a structured and controlled setting. From a neurobehavioral perspective, the effectiveness of this approach may be explained by several mechanisms. First, controlled exposure to previously anxiety-inducing stimuli facilitated systematic desensitization, reducing the conditioned fear response. Second, the immersive environment enhanced the patient's sense of predictability and control, key factors known to modulate anxiety responses in pediatric populations.[8] Third, the narrative reconstruction of the clinical experience enabled cognitive reappraisal, transforming the perception of dental treatment from a threatening event into an understandable and manageable process. A key differentiating aspect of this case is the shift from passive distraction to active behavioral conditioning supported by immersive technology. [9] This distinction is clinically relevant, as it suggests that AI-based environments may not only reduce immediate anxiety but also contribute to sustained behavioral change. The observed transition from Frankl I behavior—characterized by refusal, crying, and resistance—to cooperative behavior supports this hypothesis and highlights the potential of immersive technologies to enhance traditional behavior management

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strategies. [10] Additionally, the decision to fractionate the pulpectomy procedures into multiple short sessions played a complementary role in maintaining emotional stability and preventing behavioral regression. While some approaches prioritize treatment completion in minimal visits, evidence suggests that prolonged or highly demanding sessions may increase psychological stress in young patients. In this case, the staged approach allowed for progressive reinforcement of adaptive behaviors, consolidating positive experiences across appointments.[11] Family involvement also emerged as a critical modulating factor. Parental attitudes and anxiety levels are known to influence children's emotional responses to dental care. The active participation of the patient's caregiver, combined with guidance on positive communication, likely contributed to reinforcing the behavioral improvements observed during treatment. [12] From a clinical perspective, the successful completion of multiple pulpectomies and restorative procedures without pharmacological intervention underscores the effectiveness of combining structured behavioral techniques with immersive digital tools.[13] Importantly, the favorable outcome cannot be attributed solely to the operative procedures, but rather to the interaction between clinical management, behavioral conditioning, and emotional adaptation facilitated by the virtual environment. [14] Nevertheless, this report has inherent limitations. As a single case report, the findings cannot be generalized, and the observed behavioral improvements may also be influenced by factors such as natural emotional maturation or symptom relief following emergency treatment. [15] Furthermore, the specific contribution of the immersive environment cannot be isolated from other behavioral techniques applied.

Future research should focus on controlled clinical studies to evaluate the effectiveness of AI-based immersive environments compared to conventional behavioral management strategies, as well as their long-term impact on dental anxiety and patient cooperation.[16]

These findings support the integration of emerging digital technologies into routine pediatric dental practice, particularly in patients with high levels of dental anxiety

4. Conclusions:

This case report demonstrates that structured behavioral conditioning is a critical component in the successful management of pediatric patients with early childhood caries and severe dental anxiety. The implementation of non-pharmacological behavior guidance techniques enabled a progressive transformation from definitely negative behavior to cooperative engagement, allowing the completion of complex dental procedures without the need for sedation or general anesthesia. The integration of an AI-based immersive virtual environment as an adjunct to

conventional behavioral strategies enhanced emotional regulation, improved procedural understanding, and reduced anticipatory anxiety. This approach facilitated a shift from passive behavioral management toward active cognitive-emotional conditioning, supporting both immediate cooperation and positive long-term attitudes toward dental care. Although limited by its single-case design, this report suggests that immersive digital technologies may represent a promising complementary tool in pediatric dentistry. Their incorporation into structured behavioral protocols has the potential to improve clinical outcomes while minimizing the need for pharmacological interventions.

Clinical Implications

- AI-based immersive environments can be effectively integrated into behavioral management protocols to enhance patient cooperation in pediatric dentistry.
- Structured behavioral conditioning combined with immersive technologies may reduce the need for sedation in highly anxious pediatric patients.
- Gradual exposure supported by virtual simulation can improve emotional adaptation and facilitate acceptance of complex dental procedures.
- Family involvement remains a critical factor in reinforcing positive behavioral outcomes and long-term adherence to oral health care.

Contributions of the authors

LIP contributed to the conception and design of the study, data acquisition, and drafting of the manuscript. LIP, AV, ABM, ACH, and BVR contributed to the literature review and data interpretation. All authors critically revised the manuscript for important intellectual content and approved the final version.

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